

Studies in the Anthraquinone Series. Condensation of 3 : 5-Dinitrophthalic Acid with Toluene,

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The hydroxyanthraquinones are abundant in nature usually in the form of glucosides, from which important compounds like alizarin, purpurin, etc., are obtained. On account of the valuable tinctorial and medicinal properties exhibited by many of these, the study of their composition and synthesis has long been a subject of considerable interest.

The condensation of nitrophthalic anhydrides with phenols and hydrocarbons and the subsequent conversion of the resulting nitrobenzoylbenzoic acids into hydroxyanthraquinones is one of the various methods available for the synthesis of these substances. The position of the hydroxyl-groups in the resulting anthraquinone can be ascertained from a knowledge of the position of the nitro-groups in the phthalic anhydride molecule and the manner in which the nitrophthalic anhydrides condense with the reacting substances. So, it would be of interest to study the influence of nitro-groups on the condensation of nitrophthalic anhydrides with other bodies.

Mitter and Sarkar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930,7, 619,) found that 3-and 4-nitrophthalic anhydrides condense with toluene to give the compounds (I) and (II) respectively.

It would appear from these observations that of the two carboxyl groups, the one nearer to a nitro-group is more reactive than the other.

Eder and Widmer (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 5, 3) found that with 3-nitrophthalic acid and *m*-cresol two nitrobenzoylbenzoic acids are obtained.

So the nature of the substance reacting has also some influence on the nature of the product formed. The same authors (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1923, 6, 966) condensed *m*-cresol with 3:5-dinitrophthalic anhydride and here they obtained only one product, *viz.*,

in the formation of which the contiguity of the nitro-group to the carboxyl group was probably the determining factor.

When 3:5-dinitrophthalic anhydride is condensed with toluene in presence of aluminium chloride only one product is obtained which may have either of the two formulae.

After reducing the nitro-groups a diamino-acid is obtained which is converted into a diaminoanthraquinone by the action of sulphuric acid. On diazotisation a dihydroxyanthraquinone is obtained which is identical with the dihydroxymethylantraquinone obtained by the condensation of 3:5-dihydroxybenzoic acid with *p*-toluic acid (Marchlewski, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 1137). The condensation product of 3:5-dinitrophthalic anhydride with toluene has therefore the formula (III), the anhydride behaving with toluene in the same way as

with *m*-cresol. The contiguity of a nitro-group is here the determining factor in the reactivity of a carboxyl group.

EXPERIMENTAL.

3:5-Dinitrophthalic Anhydride.—*3:5-Dinitro-*o*-toluic acid* (5 g.) prepared by the method of Jacobsen and Wierss (*Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 1956) was oxidised according to the method of Racine (*Annalen*, 1887, **239**, 71) by heating in a sealed tube with dilute nitric acid (25 c.c., *d* 1.15) to 170° for six hours instead of at 160° for five hours as suggested by the author. The slight modification is found to improve the yield.

The well-dried acid is refluxed with five times its weight of acetic anhydride for about an hour. The excess of acetic anhydride is distilled off at a reduced pressure. The residue is recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 162-64°.

*3:5-Dinitro-2-*p*-toluoylbenzoic Acid*.—*3:5-Dinitrophthalic anhydride* (5 g.) is suspended in toluene (75 c.c.) and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (20 g.) gradually added to the mixture with constant shaking, in about two hours. The reaction takes place at the ordinary temperature. The excess of toluene is distilled off in steam, the crude acid boiled with calcium carbonate, filtered and acidified. It is recrystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow plates, m.p. 237°. (Found: C, 54.53; H, 3.35; N, 8.53; M. W. (by titration), 330. $C_{15}H_{10}O_7N_2$ requires C, 54.54; H, 3.03; N, 8.48 per cent., M. W. 330).

*3:5-Diamino-2-*p*-toluoylbenzoic Acid*.—To a solution of ferrous sulphate (70 g.) in 50 c.c. of water, heated to boiling, liquor ammonia (120 c.c.) is added and then an ammoniacal solution of *3:5-dinitro-2-*p*-toluoylbenzoic acid* is slowly poured in, the mixture being

well-shaken all the time. When the reaction is complete, the mixture is heated to boiling for about fifteen minutes and filtered. The residue is repeatedly extracted with boiling water and the combined filtrates evaporated to a small volume on the water-bath. This is filtered and after digesting with animal charcoal the filtrate is acidified with dilute acetic acid when a semi-solid precipitate is obtained which solidifies on drying on a porous plate. Yellow needles from water, m.p. 170-71°. (Found: N, 10.55; M. W., 269. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 10.37 per cent., M. W., 270).

1:3-Diamino-6-methylanthraquinone.—The diamino-acid obtained in the previous operation (1 g.) is added to strong sulphuric acid (d 1.84) heated to 160° in an oil-bath and kept at 160-70° for twenty minutes. On pouring on ice a red mass separates which is extracted with dilute soda solution. The residue crystallises from pyridine in fine red needles, m.p. 265°. (Found: N, 11.45. $C_{15}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.11 per cent.).

1:3-Dihydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone.—Diaminoanthraquinone (0.5 g.) was dissolved in strong sulphuric acid (5 g.) and the calculated amount of powdered sodium nitrite was added with constant stirring under ice-cooling until an excess of nitrous acid was detected by starch-iodide paper. The mixture was then heated on the water-bath for an hour and then poured on ice. The precipitate was filtered, washed, dried on a porous plate and extracted with benzene. On recrystallisation from the same solvent, the melting point was found to be 267° which was not altered on mixing with an equal amount of 1:3-dihydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone obtained by condensing 3:5-dihydroxybenzoic acid with *p*-toluic acid. Hence it was concluded that the two substances must be identical. The quantity of the substance was not sufficient for an analysis.